

METHODS TO COMMUNICATE IN LEARNING LESSONS THROUGH MOVIES AND VIDEOS.

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Abstract: This article discusses the value of using movies and films in the classrooms. Although different scholars have defined the term, all of them share the fact that authentic materials have been exposed to real language and are used in their respective communities. Authentic materials are mostly used for interpersonal communication.

Key words: authentic materials, structure, functions, content, learning, communication, video and movies, motivation, non-native speakers, create, project.

Movies and videos play a significant role in teaching and learning classes that use authentic materials, as was clear from the previous chapter's wealth of information regarding their significance, types, advantages, and downsides. Because students may learn a lot from viewing English movies, including pronunciation, vocabulary, style, intonation, and even western culture and habits, English movies and videos are becoming more and more popular and well-known in Uzbekistan these days. Additionally, students see a variety of educational films, each of which contains information that helps viewers become better social learners. Learning through movies can help students become more socially adept by teaching them how to interact with various types of people and cultural norms. In shortly, using movies in class can be engaging and helpful for students.

Movies are an excellent example of real-life material that may be used in language instruction to make the process more fun, interesting, and perhaps even a little bit easier. McGovern [7; 19–27] underlines that movies are made to fully and directly evoke viewers' emotions. Regarding movies, the element of enjoyment is also very much present. Since the use of movies in language learning involves emotive factors, it is crucial for the instructor to be able to strike a balance between engaging the students in the movies and using the movies' capacity for language learning. Thus, using movies as authentic material requires an emphasis on the teaching approach, which should be content- and task based. In addition, also the teachers own attitude towards the movies is an important factor in order to be able to treat the movies as cultural items instead of mere sources of language input.

Gerhard's first category is about real listening and viewing content, which includes TV, movies, videos, and clips. It also primarily concludes our research paper. We'll discuss the value of using listening and viewing materials in the classroom in the paragraph that follows. Using movies and videos authentic materials offers several advantages in the English classes. Movies and videos are not only very useful for language teachers, but also to motivate students. When students are motivated by movies or videos, the learning process is better, easier and more natural. Furthermore, there are given some points about using movies and videos in language learning. Students are able to watch movies or videos, and listen to the natural flow and rhythm of English in real life. This gets students ready to communicate as

well as improve their intonation and pronunciation Porcel C. explains that practicing with authentic materials such as videos or movies encourages learners of a foreign language to experience the target language. Authentic contribute a great deal to students' language learning. Littlewood [6; 147-151] supports this idea further by explaining that authentic materials contribute to social interaction and functional communication activities, which support students to communicate immediately outside the classroom. Stempleski S [12; 73] state that movie clips present communicative situations and bring native speakers into the classroom via video. In addition, video shows students culture so they can learn how people live, what they eat and what they wear. Lonergan J.[5; 266] and McGovern [7; 19] add that film clips create a climate for successful learning in classrooms. Similarly, learning in a positive atmosphere helps students reduce anxiety and encourages them to acquire language. Sherman J [10; 23] adds that video clips contain everything needed in a class. Teachers can use for discussion, writing assignments and input for project.

The use of films and videos in the classroom is crucial for enhancing students' viewing and listening abilities. As indicated above, students who watch or listen to a lot of movies or videos strengthen their listening skills as well as their intonation and pronunciation. We should also understand how to use real listening and viewing materials for communicating.

According to Hill [4; 246], teachers can create listening assignments by letting students watch and listen to movies to understand what characters are saying. Students then check off sheets to show who spoke which sentences. The use of movies, say Stemleski and Tomalin [7; 196], can improve pupils' writing abilities. For instance, teachers may challenge students to predict what will happen in the following scene while pausing at a current scene. When a visual is paused, students can also describe the feelings of the characters. As was already indicated, students are provided chances to develop their communicative abilities until they become fluent in the language as a result of vocabulary and communicative activities. As a result, pupils can study independently and speak the target language. Nunan [8; 173] explains that "scaffolding" is the process of encouraging and assisting pupils to acquire language before they can carry out a task and communicate using language. Up until they are capable of speaking the language independently, students are prepared. When pupils no longer require it, the scaffolding will be gradually removed.

In any case, using movies in the classroom is challenging. They can be challenging at times, but Western films, for instance, are simple to grasp because of the amount of action they contain. Some other movies have obvious conventional narratives that are simple to follow, such as love romances, epics, and science fiction dramas. The subtitles and dubbing, which may be in English, are quite important. Depending on the method teachers choose to employ, they significantly aid in the goal of assisting English language acquisition through films. Sometimes instructors advise students to see a movie with subtitles or dubbing before watching it in English. Finding English-language movies with English subtitles would be fantastic. They facilitate language comprehension because it is more challenging to understand spoken language than written expressions because the words are matched with images and voices.

As was previously stated, watching movies is crucial for enhancing our speaking and listening abilities. Students who pay close attention to the native-speaking actors will learn the precise pronunciation and appropriate use of language in a variety of contexts. Then, as Porcel [9; 23] suggests, students will practice their pronunciation even while they are viewing a movie in silence. "Movies make the learner's articulatory organs work even when the learner is merely

watching the movies silently," he writes. This is demonstrated by their silent (covert) impersonation of the speakers' utterances and pronunciation without making a sound. Their speech and intonation will be improved the greatest by doing this.

Additionally, speaking is a crucial ability while using movies as teaching and learning resources. With the help of pronunciation, students can learn how to pronounce words correctly. This allows them to carefully listen to movies and then attempt to directly mimic the word pronunciation. They can thus improve their speaking skills and use them in their daily lives.

The following are other reasons why watching English movies will provide learners more opportunity to speak English properly:

- a. Learners learn the vocabulary. When speaking, native speakers frequently utilize words and expressions that are not found in books.
- b. Students study how to pronounce these words in native English. Not only can movies help students with grammar and vocabulary, but also with pronunciation. If they listen to English spoken by Americans or Britons, they can learn to speak like them.
- c. The learner will be capable of comprehending spoken language. Movies aren't created for English language learners; they're made for native speakers. As a result, the actors speak quickly, just like native speakers do in real life.

Teachers must be aware of various accents, dialects, slang, and regional vernacular when using video clips, though, as these can make it difficult for students to learn English [3; 148-156]. Students may handle movies the same way they treat watching television at home. Therefore, rather than just letting them unwind, teachers must focus their students' attention to the content and language in movies [2; 96]. The role of the teacher is to encourage pupils' eyes, ears, and minds to take in information; otherwise, they will passively observe as though it were simply entertainment [11; 364-367].

Movies may be a fun and inspiring teaching tool for students of all skill levels. The learners are given real-life language input through movies, which may be challenging to obtain in a non-English speaking environment. Additionally, numerous earlier research have found a number of benefits of using movies in foreign language instruction. Authenticity, the caliber and quantity of the input that movies offer, and the many positive benefits that movies have on language learning—like the exposure to a foreign language and the fun element of movies—are a few of these factors. Since using movies as a teaching tool also has an impact on these factors, discussions of various learning styles and brain use are also included.

According to Porcel [9; 23], there are three crucial requirements for effective education through the use of movies. First, there are the conventional films that are both enjoyable and instructional. Second, the learner must have a useful workbook to use as a guide while getting ready to watch. Third, multiple classroom activities must be combined with movies.

We thought of writing about several kinds of videos. The interaction in educational videos will only increase. The most recent developments include interactive videos, which give viewers more control over what they watch and if they wish to replay specific sections, among other things. The ability for people with minimal technical knowledge (other than the ability to operate a computer) to create web movies using personalized video templates, such as These animated videos (for educational purposes), make the subject matter more engaging for the learner, is one of the other major advancements.

These are excellent strategies for encouraging English language learners to learn. It takes a distinct perspective on how to assist students. Any way to support these students in achieving academic success is always beneficial. In addition, watching English-language educational films aids adult learners in better understanding and recognizing the many cultures and values. Additionally, they learn how to interact and converse with others from different backgrounds. Through the examination and comprehension of the film's objective, students are able to understand the educational material indirectly.

World cultures and societies are described in informative films. These films depict the struggles that residents of different nations experience on a daily basis.

A sort of action known as entertainment is one that captivates a crowd and keeps them interested or entertained. It can be a task or an idea, but it's more likely to be one of the things that have evolved over the course of thousands of years particularly for the aim of holding an audience's attention. The majority of entertainment forms are identifiable and familiar, even when people's attention is diverted by various things due to individual preferences in entertainment. Therefore, watching a good movie when we're fatigued improves our mood. We may put our concerns aside and just laugh and grin while watching enjoyable movies.

Students' ability to improve their communication skills was aided, encouraged, and given opportunities by the usage of movies and videos. Students were provided opportunity to practice their communication abilities before being given tasks to communicate in English at the postviewing stage. This was done until they had gathered language knowledge from vocabulary, sentence structures, and communicative activities. Students might therefore use the provided photographs to compose stories, invent dialogue, or do a role-play in front of the class. According to [1; 173], scaffolding is the process of assisting children in acquiring language skills before they can carry out a task and use the language to communicate.

The mood in the language classroom was made more casual by watching English language movies or videos. Students' nervousness can be reduced and their motivation to learn the language is increased when they are learning in a relaxed setting. They don't hesitate to ask any questions about the sessions because they are at ease learning the language. There is no tension in the classroom.

Learning English through videos or films boosts students' proficiency in speaking the language. Teaching using movies also aids pupils in gaining confidence in their English communication abilities. Students actively participate in language-based activities in class without showing any signs of shyness. Videos and movies used as teaching tools aid students in developing their public speaking skills.

Students were exposed to the target language both within and outside of the classroom through the use of movies. Students are motivated to speak in the target language through engaging and varied tasks and communicative activities inside the classroom. Native speakers and the communicative situation are successfully introduced into the classroom [13; 70–73]. It significantly aids students in their language acquisition.

In conclusion, movies help students translate words into images since, according to some academics, reading comprehension depends on the ability to imagine. The ability to recall information is improved by watching movies. Students can become proficient at using movies as a listening, speaking, and writing approach independently with some practice.

References:

1. Carter, R., & Nunan, D. (Eds.) (2001). The Cambridge guide to teaching English to speakers of other languages.
2. Harmer, J. [2007a]. How to teach English. Harlow: Pearson/Longman.
3. Harmer, J. [2007b]. The practice of English language teaching
4. Hill, B. [1992]. Making the most of video (2nd ed.). London:
5. Lonergan, J. [1984]. Video in language teaching. Cambridge
6. Littlewood, W. [2010]. Communicative language teaching: Cambridge
7. McGovern, J. [1083]. Video applications in English language teaching. Oxford
8. Nunan, D. [1999]. Second language teaching and learning. Boston
9. Porcel, C. [2009]. Using films in class. Modern English Teacher, 18(3), 24-29.
10. Sherman, J. [2003]. Using authentic video in the language classroom
11. Stempleski, S. [2011]. Methodology in language teaching: An anthology of current practice (pp.364-367). Cambridge
12. Stempleski, S., & Arcario, P. (Eds.). [1992]. Video in second language teaching: Using, selecting, and producing video for the classroom.
13. Stempleski, S., & Tomalin, B. [2001]. Resource books for teachers: Film.